

Marietta L. Johnson's Early 'Organic Education' Work

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Abstract

Until recently it was not known that Marietta Johnson, founder of the School of Organic Education in Fairhope, Alabama already wrote about her pedagogical principles and her school earlier than 1913. Between 1909 and 1913 Johnson also gave lectures. This case study highlights the reasons. It also gives an overview of Johnson's pre-1913 published work.

Key Words: *Marietta Louise (Pierce) Johnson (1864-1938), Stanwood Cobb (1881-1982), Charles Hanford Henderson (1861-1941), John Franklin Johnson (1860-1919), Eugene Randolph Smith (1876-1968). Bureau of Educational Experiments; Organic Education; Progressive Education; School of Organic Education, Fairhope.*

Introduction: Progressive Education

“Educational institutions should serve the needs of every individual, should meet the demands of every child, rather than require the child to meet the demands of the institution.”

Marietta Johnson in *The Oswego Daily Palladium* (September 1, 1911, p. 10).

“Not only must the child be happy and intelligent, but the school work must *preserve* and perfect the entire *organism*, hence the term ‘organic.’”

Marietta Johnson cited in *The Burning Question* (Luttinger, 1913, p. 18).

In April 1919, Marietta Louise (Pierce) Johnson, principal of the School of Organic Education, Fairhope, Alabama and four other progressive educators founded the Association for the Advancement of Progressive Education — shortened to Progressive Education Association (PEA) in 1920, and renamed American Education Fellowship in 1944. Historians of education state that Marietta Johnson who in 1919 was principal of schools in two different states — one in Fairhope Alabama, a second in Greenwich, Connecticut — was mastermind of the idea to set up a countrywide progressive education organization.

Three versions of her contribution to the founding of the PEA exist:

1. Historian of education Graham (1967) concludes that after she first suggested to Cobb to found a progressive education society, Marietta Johnson changed her plan into “a proposal to establish an educational association devoted to publicizing current experiments in education” (p. 18). According to Graham, Cobb approved Johnson's new scheme.
2. Historian of education Cremin (1961), on the other hand, believes that after considering Marietta Johnson's initial idea Cobb dropped it “in favor of a broader sort of conference in which various experimental educators and parent groups might gather to exchange ideas” (p. 242). Essentially, this second story credits *Mr. Cobb*, not *Mrs. Johnson*.
3. Recently, a third version came into sight. It is my observation, based on analysis of the archives of the NYC Bureau of Educational Experiments (BEE) that Marietta Johnson — a non-resident Bureau member in 1917 and 1918 — must have handed Cobb a kind of carbon copy of an idea for a conference, originally suggested by consulting BEE researcher Gertrude Hartman to her Bureau co-workers during a January 1918 meeting (consult Staring, 2013, 2014). Johnson knew that Hartman was planning a conference *along with* a national association of teachers of experimental schools. Minutes of the specific January 1918 Bureau meeting read, “Miss Hartman is arranging *a conference of teachers of experimental schools with a view to forming an association of such teachers* working in close cooperation with the Bureau in its surveys, its publications, its library, and its experiments” (Minutes Department of Information, 01-17-1918; BEE Archives in Bank Street College of Education; italics added). In her capacity of non-resident BEE member Marietta Johnson attended Bureau meetings discussing educational renewal and other topics. It appears she successfully borrowed Gertrude Hartman's idea.

At its inception in 1919 the Progressive Education Association counted 86 members. In 1920 the PEA had over 500 members, in 1925 almost 1,700, in 1932 more than 7,500, and by the mid-1930s PEA members numbered more than 8,500.

Stanwood Cobb (1919), principal of the Chevy Chase Country Day School, Washington, D.C., one of five PEA founders, listed the names of the majority of the initial PEA members in the *Baltimore Sun*. Cobb himself became Executive Secretary. Members of the PEA Executive Committee were, amongst others, Marietta L. Johnson and Eugene R. Smith. Charles Hanford Henderson, amongst others, was a member of the Advisory Council. These names we will encounter more than once in the paragraphs below.

A year later, Cobb (1920) exemplified PEA endorsed novel teaching methods in a number of so-called ‘new schools.’ His article appeared in the women’s magazine *Good Housekeeping*. He described how the Moraine Park School of Dayton, Ohio had its inception in the mind of a parent, an engineer, Arthur E. Morgan, who together with other parents sent a questionnaire to well-known educationalists inviting suggestions for the school’s educational approach. (Morgan had earlier sent his son Ernest to Marietta Johnson’s Fairhope School of Organic Education). Cobb explained the unique financing of the school — fees proportioned to the parents’ income — and he elucidated that the school’s teachers as well as teachers of other schools in Cincinnati, Cleveland and Grand Rapids, similar to the Moraine Park School, followed a new teaching method — the ‘Project Method.’

When a boy comes to the school he is studied carefully to see what he is most interested in, and in what direction his talents lie. Then he is asked to choose some project along the lines of his talents...When he has thus selected a goal for himself, he goes at his work with a good deal of self-direction. The teacher appears to him as a guide rather than a taskmaster...Interest and enthusiasm are aroused at the outset and the task, being of the boy’s own imposition, is labored at cheerfully and ungrudgingly. In the course of developing his project, the boy receives his education. (p. 59).

Additionally, Cobb focused on Eugene Randolph Smith’s teaching methods at Park School, Baltimore, Maryland — not based on the Project Method, but on other educational approaches, *e.g.*, dividing classes into groups organized to study various aspects of the same subject, or learning through using games, dramatization, or pageants. While light-heartedly changing the title of John Dewey’s 1916 *Democracy and Education* into the heading ‘Democracy in Education,’ Cobb indicated that the “doctrine of progressive education is that in intellectual, as in physical development, appetite and desire are the great factors in assimilation and growth;” that the subject of education “must be related somehow to life and the world about the child” (p. 201); that freedom as well as self-government, self-control and social conscience of students are fundamental; that so-called ‘progressive schools’ had movable furniture, and that students were free to move about.

Cobb quoted Park School’s principal Smith:

“If the teacher starts the children to thinking, investigating, and doing, in place of just learning by rote, all the intense interest and curiosity of childhood become an asset, in place of a drag.” (p. 201).

One year later, in the *Atlantic Monthly*, while addressing the supporting of a ‘new movement in education,’ Cobb (1921) again stressed movable furniture, stating, “In a progressive school there are no fixed desks. All the furniture is movable” (p. 228). He added, “Much of the nervousness of American school-children can be attributed to the brutal (so it will seem a hundred years from now) custom of holding them to fixed seats, — six rows, seven in a row, — for five hours a day” (p. 233). Next to the freedom of physical movement, according to Cobb, there should be mental freedom. Even though the curriculum in many progressive schools parallels the curriculum in public schools, “in all progressive schools *the aim is to have interest aroused before work is assigned*” (p. 229). Cobb listed four ‘devices’ used by educators in progressive schools when stimulating and enlivening the students’ interests and motivation and focusing their attention:

- a. Competitive games offering opportunity for physical action.
- b. No formal recitation.
- c. Flexible programmes.
- d. Connections between book-knowledge and the daily life of students.

Cobb explained that progressive schools should strive for smaller classes and all-round development of the students — meaning physical, mental, emotional, social, and aesthetic development, with

opportunities for learning self-control and self-government (compare Hissong, 1932). In addition, Cobb — in his capacity as first PEA Executive Secretary — aided in formulating PEA pedagogical principles. In his *The New Leaven*, Cobb (1928) listed ten principles, which at the outset of the PEA in 1919 represented an amalgamated view of 32 progressive educators, including Marietta L. Johnson:

1. Health must come first.
2. Learning comes from doing: let the hands aid the brain.
3. The classroom should be freed from unnatural restraints and exterior compulsions transformed into interior compulsions.
4. Adapt education to the differences of the individual child.
5. Group-consciousness and social-mindedness should be developed in children: social adjustment and character training are as important as academic progress.
6. The child should have abundant opportunity for creative expression.
7. Enable the child to acquire thorough control of the tools of learning rather than merely to acquire facts.
8. Introduce into academic work the method of creative expression, so that education shall be joyous.
9. Abolish the tyranny of marks and examinations. And finally,
10. The teacher should be a leader and guide, not a taskmaster.

These initial PEA principles, which were heavily influenced by Marietta Johnson's educational views and values, would form the foundation of the later official PEA principles. Headmaster of Park School Eugene Smith headed the committee that in 1920 translated and delineated the above ten principles into seven PEA-endorsed principles. Between 1924 and 1929, the PEA journal *Progressive Education* printed them on the inside cover of their issues:

1. Freedom to develop naturally.
2. Interest, the motive of all work.
3. The teacher a guide, not a taskmaster.
4. Scientific study of pupil development.
5. Greater attention to all that affects the child's physical development.
6. Co-operation between school and home to meet the needs of child life. And lastly,
7. The progressive school, a leader in educational movements.

Marietta L. Johnson: Powerful Educational Reformer

According to Cobb (1920), early twentieth century changes in teaching methods were predominantly due to the influence of female teachers. He observed,

For the first time women are not only teaching, but are determining methods, and are leading the way to a wholly new type of education...It is significant that if one should name the four who have been the greatest influence in this new movement — John Dewey, Hanford Henderson, Maria Montessori, and Marietta L. Johnson — two of them are women. (p. 205).

This article focuses on Marietta Johnson and her early development as progressive educator. In November 1907, Marietta Johnson (*Figure 1*), co-founder of the Progressive Education Association in 1919, had founded the School of Organic Education in the so-called 'single tax colony' in Fairhope, Alabama, a small village on the Gulf Coast. Fairhope housed the Fairhope Single Tax Corporation, the first utopian single tax colony inspired by the ideas of political economist Henry George (1879). The Corporation owned the land, which it rented out. Rather than taxing the output of labor and capital, George proposed a *single tax on land* to meet costs of running government and community (*Pensacola Journal*, 1913).

Figure 1: Marietta L. Johnson. *The New York Tribune*, June 14, 1914.

Historians of education remark that on March 16, 1913, the *New York Times* ran a full-page illustrated interview with Marietta Johnson (see Edwards, 1913). According to them this was the very first article in a high-ranking East Coast newspaper that paid attention to the Fairhope School of Organic Education. The article had a major impact. Later that year, in December, *The Survey* issued Marietta Johnson's (1913) article "Education as Growth" — according to historians of education her first account about the School of Organic Education in Fairhope. However, between 1910 and 1913, renowned East Coast newspapers, Quaker magazines, and above all, extremely influential women's magazines had already drawn attention to Johnson, her views, and her school (e.g., Bennett, 1912; Herring, 1910; Potter, 1911, 1912; Smith, 1910; see also Staring 2013, 2014). And another fact, which contradicts the opinion of prominent historians of education: in 1910 the *Journal of Education* had already issued a report about the school, written by Marietta Johnson (1910c)! In fact, diverse groups of people like members of women's clubs, readers of women's magazines, readers of several large East Coast newspapers, readers of at least one West Coast newspaper, readers of several Mid- and North-western newspapers, as well as readers of Southern newspapers, readers of Quaker magazines, members of the Woman's Christian Temperance Union, educators, members of Home and School Associations, Georgists and 'single taxers,' and others, knew about the school, its curriculum, and its founder well before Edwards' (1913) article appeared in the *New York Times* in 1913.

How has this come about? How has Marietta Johnson managed to establish her experimental school — an educational institution manifestly built on a progressive curriculum, serving the needs and demands of every individual student?

Marietta Johnson: Early Career as a Teacher

Marietta Louise Pierce was born in 1864 near St. Paul, Minnesota, daughter of Rhoda Mathilda (Morton) Pierce and Clarence D. Pierce. Marietta's mother was a teacher, her father died when she was still young. As a child Marietta attended the Christian Church (Disciples of Christ). In 1881, she graduated with honours from Humboldt School in St. Paul, Minnesota. Four years later, in 1885, she graduated from State Normal School at St. Cloud, Minnesota. Next, Marietta Pierce taught at rural Minnesota elementary schools for five years. Later she began training prospective teachers at St. Paul State Normal School (1890-1892), at Moorhead State Normal School (1892-1896), and at Mankato State Normal School (1896-1899).

In June 1897, Marietta L. Pierce was married to John Franklin ('Frank') Johnson (1860-1919), carpenter and cabinetmaker (Figure 2). The couple first lived in Mankato, Minnesota where Marietta had a kind of 'conversion experience' after reading Robert Nathan Oppenheim's (1898) *The Development of the Child*. (Oppenheim was attending physician of the Children's Department of the New York City Red Cross Hospital and New York City's Children Hospital.) In her autobiography *Thirty Years with an Idea*, Marietta Johnson reported that reading Oppenheim's book incited her to re-examine her sense of life as well as her career.

I discovered that nearly everything I had been doing with such pride and success in the primary department [at Mankato State Normal School; J.S.] was a violation of the order of the development of the nervous system. I realized that my enthusiasm was destructive, and the more efficient I was, the more I injured the pupils! (Johnson, 1974, p. 8).

It is interesting to note here that she immediately began re-assessing the prevailing educational practice. For example, *School Education* (1900, p. 6) and *St. Paul Globe* (1899) referenced her words of critique during “Some of the Laws of the Development of the Nervous System Considered In Their Relation to School Work,” a joint session of the Elementary and Child Study Sections at a conference held at the Central Presbyterian Church in St. Paul. The *St. Paul Globe* (1899) cited Johnson:

“If drawing, reading, writing and such studies are dangerous for the child of seven,” remarked [Marietta Johnson] rather plaintively yesterday at the joint session of the elementary and child study sections, “and if the state of Minnesota insists, as it does, that the child of seven must attend school, will somebody please say what should be done with the child?”...In discussing drawing Mrs. Johnson thought it a mistake to place an object before the child and have him draw it as it is rather than as he sees it. It had an injurious effect on the nervous system, compelling the child to do that which was unnatural to him.

Around the turn of the century, Marietta Johnson resigned her work at Mankato State Normal, and she and Frank moved to North Dakota. In spring 1901, she gave birth to their first son, Clifford Ernest (*Figure 3*). In autumn 1901, they moved to St. Paul, where she resumed teaching at the State Normal School. By the end of 1902, they then moved to Fairhope, Alabama, where Marietta in 1903 taught at the Fairhope elementary school, and where she befriended former teacher of physical culture Lydia Jane Newcomb Comings and her husband Samuel Huntington Comings. They had lengthy mutually inspiring conversations about Froebel, manual training, open-air schooling and other educational renewal issues. In 1904, the Johnson family moved to a pecan farm in Barnett, Mississippi where Marietta in 1905 gave birth to Franklin Pierce, their second son (*Figure 3*). The same year, Fairhope friend Samuel Comings (1904) would publish *Pagan vs. Christian Civilization* — an essay on experimental industrial and vocational education. In 1907, the Johnsons moved back to Fairhope. Although the official history of education tells that Lydia Comings had invited the Johnson family to return to Fairhope, a 1920 *Evening Post Magazine* mentions an alternative reason: Marietta and Frank were planning to raise the “pecan nut which, while not large in itself, was supposed to be a maker of large fortunes. It was for this reason that [Marietta Johnson’s] school was started in the Sunny South” (Rawson, 1920).

Figure 2: John Franklin Johnson. *The Pensacola Journal*, October 5, 1913.

Marietta Johnson's school in Fairhope, Alabama

Besides studying Oppenheim's 1898 book, Marietta Johnson studied other works about child development, for instance, George Thomas White Patrick's 1899 essay 'Should Children Under Ten Learn To Read And Write?' (Patrick was professor of philosophy at State University of Iowa, Iowa City, Iowa.) Charles Hanford Henderson's 1902 *Education and the Larger Life* particularly strengthened her 1898 choice of new pedagogical direction (Bennett, 1914). Johnson (1974) later wrote in her autobiography:

[Henderson] not only agreed with Oppenheim as to the nature of the growing child and the insistence that the adult's supreme responsibility is to supply the right conditions of growth, but suggested a practical program — life-giving to body, mind, and spirit. This idea took possession of me and I could not rest until I had started a school. I began experimenting with my own child and other children of the neighborhood. (p. 17).

During the late 1880s, Henderson who taught physics and chemistry at the Philadelphia Manual Training School since 1886 was developing his own approach to education. Following his appointment as principal of the Northeast Branch of the Training School in 1893, he established a new instructive program. Henderson (1896) acknowledged that "progressive education would be one in which the educational process [is] being constantly readjusted to meet...changing conditions" (p. 487) in society at large. He advocated schooling students in a physical, intellectual, and in a moral sense. Children are born investigators and inquisitive experimenters, and want "to be employed...with something that interests *them*, not something that interests mamma or papa, or the teacher" (p. 496). According to Henderson, his educational methods based on manual training and exercising the senses would lead to "the very sort of action that is educationally the most valuable — to that which is self-prompted" (p. 496). When Lecturer on Manual Training at Harvard University in Boston during 1897-98, Henderson (1898) suggested founding of manual training schools — schools of vocational education in today's terminology — that would demonstrate a laboratory character, the curriculum encompassing "gymnastic, music, manual training, free-hand drawing, and language" (p. 767). Henderson recommended implementing manual training instruction in primary and secondary education schools.

Beginning in 1897, Henderson actively endorsed his views through public lectures on what he called *Organic Education*, at first at the Boston Sloyd Training School. In the winter of 1899, following an appointment as director of the Brooklyn, New York based Pratt Institute High School he continued lecturing in Boston, this time also at the Industrial School Hall. In the fall of that year he also delivered a course of ten lectures at the Philadelphia Griffith Hall, Baptist Publication Building, illustrating his latest views on Organic Education. Although these lectures were well attended and Henderson in 1902 issued *Education and the Larger Life*, a book on his Organic Education scheme, the impact of his work and writings seems to have been rather insignificant. Even though the majority of reviews of his 1902 book was mildly positive (e.g., *Boston Evening Transcript*, 1902), *National Magazine* may well have expressed a sense of general feeling: "If the United States were heaven, and all its youths angels with a bent for knowledge, then Mr. Henderson's educational plan would be ideal...It is a lofty, stimulating but wholly impractical hope, this of *Education and the Larger Life*" (D. L. S., 1902). Still, sometimes one recognizes Henderson's authority in nonconforming situations. For instance, Harriet Forbes — in 1916 member of the NYC Bureau of Educational Experiments — together with her co-author as well her life-long companion Harriet M. Johnson — in 1916 one of three founders of the Bureau of Educational Experiments and in 1919 founder of the Bureau's Nursery School (Staring, 2013; Staring & Aldridge, 2015) — inserted a quote from Henderson's work in the title-page of their book *Home Nursing* (1905).

Henderson (1902) propagated an Organic Education roughly meaning the development of the senses, good health, and schooling of 'personal control.' He advocated implementing Organic Education in the kindergartens and schools. By November 1907, Marietta Johnson dared to found a school, its core curriculum sailing under the flag of Henderson's Organic Education (see Henderson in Comings 1915, p. 7; Johnson, 1920, 1923, 1929, 1974; *Ladies' Home Journal*, 1914; Potter, 1911; Rawson, 1920).

Even though Lydia Comings (in Comings, 1915, p. 158) indicated that Henderson first used the concept of Organic Education in his 1902 book, he had already regularly used the phrase in public lectures and articles in the late 1890s. Yet, principal of the Detroit Normal Training School Harriet Maria Scott and instructor in English of the Indianapolis High School Gertrude Buck also developed the concept — independently of Henderson — in their 1897 book *Organic Education: A Manual for Teachers in Primary and Grammar Grades*. The most likely originator of the concept and its denotations, however, was social reformer and educationalist Felix Adler who introduced ‘Organic Education’ during a conference on education in Plymouth, Massachusetts in 1894 (*New York Times*, 1894; *School Journal*, 1894).

In November 1907, Henderson, invited by the Comingses, stayed a week in Fairhope, and gave a speech at the opening of Johnson’s school. Over the first years of its existence, the school had several names, successively Comings Memorial College of Organic Education in 1908 (commemorating Samuel H. Comings who had died a month after the school had opened), School for Organic Training in 1909, College for Organic Education in 1909, Comings Memorial School of Organic Education in 1910, and lastly, as of about mid-1910, School of Organic Education (compare, for instance, *Boston Evening Transcript*, 1912; Christopher, 1910; Comings, 1938; Johnson, 1910c; Smith, 1910; *Twice-A-Week Spokesman Review*, 1910). The succession of differing names of Johnson’s school, the concepts ‘Organic Training’ (Henderson, 1902, pp. 156, 209) and ‘Organic Education’ forming part of the school’s name akin to a ship’s flag indicating where the ship is registered, as well as the fact that Henderson attended the school’s founding day, unmistakably indicate that Johnson’s school’s core curriculum sailed under the flag of Henderson’s Organic Education.

Figure 3: Photo showing Marietta and Frank Johnson’s two children: Clifford Ernest (left) and Franklin Pierce (right). Photo: J. Staring, 2015. (Courtesy Marietta Johnson Museum, Fairhope).

1908 - 1910: Lydia Comings and Marietta Johnson Begin to Promote the School

Leslie B. Shaw (1924) wrote in a book review of F. M. Alexander’s *Constructive Conscious Control of the Individual* in the August 9, 1924, *New York Evening Post Literary Review*:

In this country Mrs. Marietta Johnson of the Fairhope Organic Schools [sic] was the first to demonstrate that education must be adapted to the needs of the individual organism; and that theories beyond or outside such needs should not be formulated. It is notable, too, that in the Fairhope Organic Schools fear is never detected in the behavior of the pupils...Mr. Alexander’s teaching is precisely in this direction — the integration of the personality as the basis for education.

It should be clear, Marietta Johnson’s ideals of integrating the child’s personality as the basis for education were widely known a decade and a half after opening the doors of her school in Fairhope. How has this come about? To be specific: when and why has it begun?

During the first years of the school’s existence, Marietta Johnson was busy introducing her understanding of Henderson’s approach to education, such as not specifying single-year grade groups. Instead the four, five and six-year-olds formed the kindergarten class; and the children seven to thirteen

years of age formed the so-called ‘life class’ (Johnson, 1910c). From around 1911 onwards, the six and seven-year-olds formed the ‘first life class;’ the eight and nine-year-olds the ‘second life class;’ and so forth until ‘fourth life class’ (see Lydia Comings in Comings, 1915, pp. 182-191; Edwards, 1913; Hunt, 1913; Johnson, 1923, pp. 58-59). Henderson (1902) propagated a similar class formation:

The work itself is so largely individual that a single group may properly include children of quite unlike ages...The habit of massing together children of the same age takes away from the pleasure and picturesqueness of life, and ends by making the children themselves quite selfish and unregardful of others. (p. 190).

Johnson’s school began with only six children, including her two sons.

Our school started November 1st, 1907, with six children enrolled. We were simply trying to find out what exercises and occupations *will* make the body stronger, mind more intelligent and keep the spirit sweet, happy and sincere. We charged no tuition because the experiment was being made in the interests of the public school system, and we wished to conduct it under public school conditions. We wanted to see if the child would really learn the necessary things without all the pressure of ‘requirements,’ but by simply *meeting* his requirements, as we were able. (Johnson in Luttinger, 1913, p. 18).

Sadly, Johnson’s youngest son Franklin Pierce died of a fall only one month after the school was founded (Comings, 1938).

Around 1909, the school’s population already reached the number of fifty pupils. Distributing appealing pamphlets seems to have been part of the school’s activities to attract (boarding) students. In 1908, Lydia Comings issued *Organic Training: A Few Suggestions For Better School Methods*, a 4-pages pamphlet. This pamphlet is missing. The following year, the school issued *Comings Memorial College of Organic Education*, a prospectus that, according to *The Public* (1909), “unfolds an interesting plan for stimulating the development of childhood through self-prompted creative ability.” September and October 1909 issues of *The Public* had advertisements for the prospectus. This particular prospectus is missing too.

Lydia Comings, who allegedly encouraged Marietta Johnson to open a school, as well as other friends of Johnson’s provided the pecuniary support to run the school. In 1908, soap magnate, social reformer and philanthropist Joseph Fels made an initial donation of \$5,000, enabling the school to move to a large location in 1909. Over the next five years he would donate \$1,000 a year (Comings, 1938). The number of students increased progressively, and Johnson had to hire and train other teachers (Johnson, 1910c; Pope, 1911) in order to teach them “to know the natural development of the child’s development, hence the name ‘organic’” (Wallace, 1913). From mid-1912 onwards, Fels’s gift almost depleted, she had to secure other funds to maintain the school. Johnson did so by drawing media attention to the school, by writing applications for assistance in support of the school, as well as by giving lectures on her school and its teaching methods. Interestingly, another reason was that in 1911 the school had become “too large (150 enrolled), to do the best work with the financial support” (Johnson cited in Luttinger, 1913, p. 18). Marietta Johnson consequently reduced the number of students in 1912, meaning that she condensed school revenues too because of the decreased number of (fee paying) boarding students. Of course, she would always gladly accept donations, but the pressing need to secure funds became apparent around mid-1912.

According to her friend Lydia Comings (in Comings, 1915), Marietta Johnson began “lecturing each year in many of the larger cities” (p. 159) from 1907 onwards. Up to today, these tours are impossible to chronicle. It looks as if pre-1909 reports in newspapers outside Fairhope do not exist. On the other hand, during studying newspaper, magazine and journal reports of Johnson’s school, it became evident that during the first years of the school’s existence both Lydia Comings and Marietta Johnson promoted the school and its educational approach. It is worthy of note that their speeches and published articles up to mid-1910 predominantly discuss theoretical aspects of education, and Organic Education in particular.

An advertisement in the May 1909 *Federation Bulletin* — the official organ of the Massachusetts State Federation of Women’s Clubs — indicates that Johnson’s school offered “Natural Methods, Brain development through training of the Sense Organs. Kindergarten, “Life Class,” Advanced Classes, Normal Course for Teachers, Manual Training, School Garden, Out-door Gymnasium.” These topics time and again return in later newspaper, magazine and journal articles. The earliest story found in newspapers outside Fairhope appeared a month earlier, in April 1909, in the Syracuse, New York newspaper *Post-Standard*. In

fact it concerns a kind of hybrid story; it is a reprint of an article written by Mrs. Mary Dana Hicks Prang, spouse of art publisher Louis Prang — originally issued in the *Fairhope Courier*, yet additionally introduced by the *Post-Standard*. Mrs. Prang's (1909) report reviews an address by Marietta Johnson, date: not mentioned; topic: "What is Organic Education?" She summarized Johnson's ideals (*italics added*):

[Marietta Johnson] *aims for the sound, accomplished, beautiful body — the intelligent, creative mind — the sympathetic, reverent spirit*. She believes that it is impossible to have an unsound body and a thoroughly healthy mind, or an unsympathetic spirit and a vigorous mind. True development must come through experience, guided experience, for she desires to present the right to the children, being of the firm conviction that one cannot look upon the right and do the wrong. Herein lies a whole body of doctrine... There comes first then, if there's any first, the sound accomplished and beautiful body to be reached by bodily activities, by outdoor life, by seeing and hearing the wonders and beauties of nature, by studying the land and the water, by tasting and feeling... And in this process, every effort is made always for each one to do his best and so whether in skill or in creation, will grow individuality... As the mind grows in the pursuit of these activities comes the desire to know of the rest of the human world, to learn to read, to wish to tell also by writing, to express in figures what they have learned through experience, in weighing, measuring, etc. In the Organic School, the children do no book study until they are 10 years old... During all this, their common work and play they are led through right guidance, to regard the rights of others, to grow in loving kindness, to advance in that brotherhood which the true democracy demands, to see that one may not be by himself alone, that all should be for each other and that one should work for all... After Mrs. Johnson's glowing statement of her educational principles and desires, she gave a day's program.

It is instantaneously decipherable that Johnson was captivated by Charles Hanford Henderson's educational ideals and his formulations. Henderson (1902, p. 48) wrote, "The social purpose is a humanized world, composed of men and women and children, sound and accomplished and beautiful in body; intelligent and sympathetic in mind; reverent in spirit."

Next, "Organic Training" — the text of a paper presented by Marietta Johnson's friend and President of Fairhope's local women's club *Fifth Thursday Club* Lydia Comings at the Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Maine Federation, held in Portland, October 20-22, 1908 — in the June 1909 women's magazine *Federation Bulletin*, explicates that Organic Education amounts to "advanced kindergarten work," that is, the training of the sense organs through "self-directed activities, freedom in the school-room and without," allowing the "brain to develop without forcing and without stunting" (Comings, 1909b, p. 241). Comings explained,

Organic training stands for the individuality of the child, and have no fear but that the child trained in this way will, when he learns to use books at ten or twelve years of age, soon outstrip those who have been using books for a number of years, for, with this free, outdoor activity training, he will be sound of brawn and brain and be eager for knowledge. That, after all, is the great thing — to have a desire for better things of life. (p. 241).

Comings' June 1909 *Federation Bulletin* article likely constitutes the text of her paper titled "Organic Training" that she, according to November 26 and 28, 1908, issues of the *Pensacola Journal* presented in her capacity of National Lecturer for the Woman's Christian Temperance Union at the First Methodist Church in Pensacola, Florida on November 27, 1908. It may well also have been the text of her paper titled "Organic Training for Children" that she, according to the October 13, 1908, *Buffalo Courier* presented in November of that year at the Mothers' Club in Buffalo, New York.

In October 1909, *Federation Bulletin* had Lydia Comings' (1909a) one-page article "Organic Education," illustrating the school's transition from Organic Training to Organic Education. Comings explicated that Organic Education deals "with the present," because, according to her, "The question asked is not what is to be the future of the child, but what can we do to-day to give him a full, well-rounded, wholesome day?" (p. 33). Note her promotional words:

A day with its full complement of work such as is suited to [the child's] age and ability, with rest and play in good measure, with wholesome food and comfortable dress that in no way retards his physical growth, with such intellectual nourishment as shall tend to mental development, withal such moral teaching, both by example and precept, as shall make for the best and truest in life and character. Such a day as this has no attendant nerve strain. There is no worry about daily marks or future

examinations, no temptation to deception, for the child is considered individually, and is encouraged to someone else's standard. (p. 33).

Comings' October 1909 article in the women's magazine *Federation Bulletin* probably constitutes the text of her paper titled "Organic Education," which she according to the January 6, 1909, *Utica Daily Press* had presented at a meeting of the Educational Committee during a January 7, 1909, meeting of the New Century Club in Utica, New York.

Lastly in 1909, the November issue of *The Public* contained Marietta Johnson's article "Education. For The Public" that discusses the genesis of a New Education, or Natural Education. Johnson (1909) opened her expose by conveying her educational dream:

There are many earnest teachers who see a new day dawning for education. They see a time when there shall be no more driving of children to their tasks even by so apparently harmless incentives as "grades," "marks" or "promotions." A time when the work of the school shall really be the joyous self-expression of the child. (p. 1143).

The article (p. 1143) articulates further aspects of Johnson's dream of a New Education:

1. "The time is coming when the school shall be conscious of its whole duty to the child."
2. "A time is coming when education will be considered a process of life — the end attainable in the present, not simply a preparation for some future time."
3. "The school will be adapted to the needs of the child, not the child made to fit the school!"

Next, Johnson asked her readers to think about how her vision could be attained. However, she acknowledged right away that the dream can in fact on no account grow to be reality. "Until the earth is in possession of the entire race on equal terms, no dream of symmetrical growth or natural development can ever be realized" (p. 1143). She added,

The new education, or natural education, as some are pleased to term it, insists upon the right of the child to be well born, well housed, well fed, well clothed, to have an environment suited to his years and strength, to have everything that will help him to grow into the best possible human being. Education is right in demanding this for every child. True democracy could ask no less. But how shall it be attained? When the school is perfected, what of the home, the source of supply? Here education spells economics, the center about which all questions revolve.

Until the earth is in possession of the entire race on equal terms, no dream of symmetrical growth or natural development can ever be realized. (p. 1143).

It is obvious that Marietta Johnson's single-tax political-economic outlook interfered with her educational reverie. "Equality of opportunity must be an accomplished fact, ere education may in truth become the development of life to higher life" (p. 1143). This is a gloomy vision indeed. Note that she added even more dimness:

No effort to introduce better methods need be lost, but educators should at the same time realize that present economic injustice is the "root of the hydra," and should study the fundamental principles of economics quite as diligently as the fundamental principles of education. (p. 1144).

If Johnson meant "equality of opportunity" for all individuals regardless of ethnic origin, one dream was *not* realized. The school practiced racial segregation, never enrolling students of African-American origin, during Johnson's lifetime.

Early in January 1910, the Boston *Christian Science Monitor* (1910) had an article about Fairhope's single tax colony, accentuating that Johnson's school taught the children "how to employ their hands in the arts, as well as how to solve mathematical problems and parse sentences." In March, the Philadelphia Quaker literary magazine *The Friend* published a "Letter from Fairhope, Alabama." The letter depicts Marietta Johnson's school as follows:

One feature which particularly pleases us as Friends, is that the children are taught to answer not by saying "Yes sir," or "No ma'am," but plain "yes" and "no." There are five teachers employed in the different departments, among which are kindergarten, domestic science, manual training and others. (Smith, 1910).

In May 1910, Johnson's friend Lydia Comings delivered two presentations at the Tenth Biennial Convention of the General Federation of Women's Clubs, May 11 to May 18, in Cincinnati, Ohio, keenly promoting the school and its educational theory. Comings' lecture before the Outlook Committee, titled "Organic Training," discussed "natural training of the complete child-body, sense and brain, as opposed to the artificial training of the brain only" (Lake, 1910, p. 172). And "A New Theory in Education," Comings' lecture before the Educational Conference illustrated the Fairhope school's curriculum:

She told of a unique school in Alabama where children are in kindergartens; and then in out-door schools until 10 years of age. There are no books for these children. They are taught orally and from nature studies; and they have tennis courts, baseball, gardening and manual training. After 10 or 11 years of age they enter upon organized educational work. (Stevens, 1910, p. 482).

1910 probably was the first year of Johnson's lecture tours. Several 1910 newspaper reports support this view that is in agreement with Gaston's (1984) opinion that Johnson "spent every summer from 1910 onwards on the lecture circuit" (p. 82).

The June 17, 1910, issue of *The Public* not only announced that Marietta Johnson would address the Chicago Single Tax Club on "Organic Education" at its hall in the Schiller Building on June 17, but also published Marietta Johnson's (1910a) article "Moral Education. For the Public" — explicating her view as regards to the Moral Education League of London, which had urged introduction of formal moral and civic instruction in schools, aiming at character formation. She stated, since children learn from experience, and children who are always controlled do not develop self-control, "occupations instead of lessons" (p. 568) should be the main work of schools. Parents and teachers should not force the interests and attention of children. Instead children should be permitted more freedom and more self-prompted activities, because "only by developing abiding interests may we hope to cultivate high moral ideals" (p. 568). However, Johnson wrote, laws that are unjust, for instance laws that tax industry and put "premiums on idleness and cunning," according to her, "cannot give the youth the right idea of social justice and civic purity" (p. 569).

In July 1910, the *Boston Daily Globe* had Alice Gertrude Herring's (1910) "Children's Paradise," a two-column-long article accurately describing Johnson's school's curriculum with its "three departments, the kindergarten for children from 4 to 7 years of age, the life class for children from 7 to 13 years and the grammar and high school for those older than 13," and its principles. Herring depicted the "most interesting educational experiment in America;" a "school without marks, examinations, or promotions;" a school "with few books and with no "lessons" in the ordinary sense of the word;" a school "in which the work is made to fit the child, not the child to fit the school;" a school "in which the utmost freedom of choice and self-prompted activity are allowed;" in one word, a "paradise for school children." According to Herring, the school's contention was "that unless the work of the school makes the child happier and stronger and sweeter in every way" it was not educational. Marietta Johnson's view of Organic Education meant a "sound, accomplished, beautiful body, an intelligent, sympathetic mind, an understanding spirit — this is education." The "social spirit" was "emphasized all through the school work, giving the children the experience of cooperative, helpful effort." The article explains that work in the school's first department — the kindergarten — was comparable to that found in nearly all kindergartens.

[M]ore emphasis [is] placed on the health and happiness of the doer than on the beauty or excellence of the thing done. Much time is spent outdoors, no fine, close work is permitted and no work done for "exhibits." Dictation work, domination of the teacher and work of "selected children" are discouraged. Much liberty is allowed for self-prompted occupations, and care is used to prevent over-stimulation of the children.

Herring indicated that the self-prompted work in the school's second department — the so-called life-class — was continued as far as possible, and that in the younger group,

that is, children from 7 to 10, the work is entirely informal, no books being used at all except as the children themselves desire to learn to read. Music is taught, but consists simply of singing songs for the pleasure of singing...Literature and history are taught by storytelling...One period is devoted daily to art work...Every child has a garden plot in which he may plant what he chooses and which he cares for in his own way...An outdoor gymnasium is much enjoyed by all of the children. The girls, in proper suits, are able to attain to quite as great a degree of excellence in bodily accomplishments as the boys."

Educational circumstances differed for the older children (from ten to thirteen years of age) in this so-called life class — at that time, mid-1910, still not divided into several separate ‘life classes’ — because the pupils increasingly turned to “books for further explanation of their experiences.” Stated Herring:

In this group they often read their own stories, take a keener interest in combinations of number and often express their thoughts in writing as well in sloyd [~ manual training / woodwork; J.S.] and art work and conversation. No “lessons” are assigned or “heard”...In this group of the life class the child comes to know the value of books as helps to his understanding, and, coming to him in this informal way, gives him a joy in them and a love for them.

Herring’s text explains that both ‘life class’ groups learned poems by hearing them being recited by their teacher; that time was taken for dramatization; that the use of good English was learned by conversation; and that German was taught by conversational methods too. Herring also described an exceptionally motivating feature of Johnson’s educational approach in her school — daily trips into nature for both groups in the ‘life class.’ Herring dubbed these trips “the daily walk.”

No particular plan is followed in this walk. It is not a part of any “course” which is being followed. In the spring there are frog eggs to observe...Then the birds’ nest must be visited...Then the different birds must be found out and observed, so the interest of the daily walk is determined for weeks, not by the will of the teacher nor the “course of study,” but by the activities of the birds. If alligators have been caught by some boys, or if a new government boat is at the pier ahead, the walk will take that direction...When the flowers are in bloom, there are all the tree blossoms to hunt...After every storm, of course, the children must run to the gullies to see what the rain has done. The watersheds, river systems, etc., that are discovered afford great pleasure...In winter the trees are interesting because it takes keener eyes to identify a tree without its leaves.

The first two years of the school’s third department, the so-called ‘grammar school,’ offered pupils “two years of earnest work...in arithmetic, history, geography, etc.,” but “grades,” “marks” and promotions were absent. The school assured that “after two years of formal, serious, earnest work, the child is old and mature enough to take up the work at the high school.” And in the final two school years, the so-called ‘high school,’ sizeable liberty of choice was allowed.

Excellence of work is not determined by examination but by interest and power shown, from day to day. The teacher is more concerned with the development of the pupil than with the development of the subject. A certificate of work is given at the end of the four years, not because a certain percent has been reached in knowledge of the subjects studied, but rather because four years of time have been profitably spent in developing personal power of body, mind and spirit, through the medium of science, mathematics, literature, history, language, music, art, manual training, gardening, dramatization, sports, etc.

Herring’s July 1910 *Boston Daily Globe* article mentions yet another special feature of Johnson’s school. A teachers training class was conducted. The school’s teachers were expected to study the development of the students while giving attention to their needs at various stages of their growth. Herring ended by stating, “School must be life, not simply a preparation for life” — a plain reference to John Dewey’s 1897 *My Pedagogic Creed* dogma that education is “a process of living and not a preparation for future living” (Dewey, 1897, p. 7). Note that the November *School Education* (1910) had extracts from Herring’s article!

The following month, on August 5, the *Twice-A-Week Spokesman Review* (1910) reported that Johnson had delivered an address at the Conference on Agricultural Education, held at the University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, July 29 and 30. The newspaper wrote, “She stated that Fairhope was the only town in the United States run on a single tax plan and that the system was working out nicely there,” and that in spite of the Alabama law requiring the teaching of agriculture in its schools, Alabama school teachers “were not provided with any facilities for giving [agricultural] instruction except text books and consequently neither they nor their students had an opportunity to study growing crops” (p. 10). The official transcript of Marietta Johnson’s address in the Minnesota *Sixteenth Biennial Report of the Superintendent of Public Instruction* does not speak of Fairhope, though, or of single tax plans. Johnson (1910b) opened her address by saying, “It may be against the rules of a woman to talk,” but those rules did not withhold her to criticize Alabama’s agricultural education. She concluded her speech “I think the best thing to do is to compel

teachers to have actual experience in agriculture. Many teachers of agriculture have never had a garden — have never even raised lettuce. These teachers need not only knowledge, but experience” (p. 176).

A week later, the Columbia, Missouri *University Missourian* (1910) reported an interview with Johnson. She praised the Alabama one-tax village where she lived, and explicated her school was “a revolution from the standpoint of education,” in her own words, “another ‘crank institution.’” Note that this particular story also appeared in *Arizona Republican*, *Christian Science Monitor*, *Labor Digest*, *Commoner*, the *Brooklyn Daily Star*, the *Houston Post*, and in a variety of other newspapers. It is evident that Johnson during her lecture tour championed Fairhope’s single tax colony ideas.

Finally in 1910, the December issue of *Journal of Education* had Marietta Johnson’s (1910c) article “The School of Organic Education” — until today never referred in educational literature. The text will be quoted in its entirety.

In the village of Fairhope, across the bay from Mobile, is a little school — not to reform the children, but to reform the methods of teaching. It is called the School of Organic Education, because the aim is to make the school process minister to the perfecting of the entire organism as well as to give instruction. There is a kindergarten, for children under seven years of age, doing the usual kindergarten work, but no dictation, nor close work, nor “finished” work for exhibition is permitted. Children from seven to thirteen years of age constitute the life class, where they simply live as wholesome and happy a life as possible.

In the first division of the life class, the children under ten use no books except as they themselves desire to learn to read. Instead of the formal work of reading, writing, and number, the children have music, that is, singing pretty songs adapted to their years for the pleasure of singing, not to be able to read music or write scales. They often act out or dramatize some song or poem. Many poems are committed by the children, not as a task, but by hearing the teacher recite the same poem a number of times. They have exercises in fundamental conceptions of number daily. Story-telling occupies an important place on the program, in which the children become acquainted with all the best fairy tales, legends, folklore, and myths, and great stories of history in the most natural, delightful way, without danger of impairing the eyesight by bending over a book. Spoken language is cultivated in the story hour. German is also taught by the conversational method. One of the most delightful items of the daily program is the walk. No definite order is followed, but the direction of the walk is determined by the interest of the day. Sometimes a neighboring pond is visited to watch the development of the tadpoles into frogs. Sometimes the woods are scoured to discover the elusive pistil of the pine. The identification of trees in winter occupies many walks. In the spring the appearance daily of some new blossom occupies the interest for many years. Then there is the building of birds’ nests to watch, and all of the interesting bird life to observe. An outdoor gymnasium affords ample opportunity for acquiring many bodily accomplishments. One period daily is given to handwork, and one also to the development of conceptions of color, form, etc. Paper sloyd, cardboard, construction, scissors and paste, clay, water colors, and pencils are used. Experience in growing plants is given every child. Plots of ground are laid out, in which every child may plant what he chooses, and cultivate it in his own way with the assistance of the teacher, and the presence and activity of his fellows to stimulate his perseverance. A well-equipped manual training department affords employment for both boys and girls as soon as they are old enough to use the tools.

The older division of the life class — children from ten to thirteen years of age — continue the activities and experiences of the younger group, but come increasingly to books. Now they learn to read, if the art has not already been acquired incidentally, and the history and geography stories are now read by the children themselves. The walks are now more interesting by reference to books which explain and enlarge the child’s experiences. Fundamental conceptions of number are continued and regular number work introduced. The manual training, gardening, domestic science, art work, music, German, and gymnasium work are continued. Spoken language is continued, and written work begun in this division. No formal lessons, however, are assigned, but the children use the books with the teacher, thus learning their use, and avoiding the great waste of time which often occurs when children of this age are required to “learn lessons” by themselves. Coming into the use of books in this way, in the companionship of a sympathetic teacher, a love for books should be acquired which will be enduring. In the thirteenth or fourteenth year regular formal work is begun, and one or two years should give the child the same knowledge of the usual common school studies that is acquired in the regular eight grades of the common school.

At fourteen or fifteen the children enter the high school. Here four years of serious, earnest work in science, literature, language, and mathematics, with agriculture, domestic science, manual training, and so forth, continued, constitutes the high school course. It is not necessary to attain any particular “grade” in any subject. It is the business of the school to present the work in the best and most helpful way, and the children are given every opportunity possible for the best development of the body, mind, and spirit, and if the work is done well, and the pupils have been serious and earnest, they have gained all they can from the experiences of the four years, and all “grades” and “marks” are superfluous.

The idea is, that the educational institutions shall give to the individual the experience and exercises which are necessary for his best development at the particular stage in which he happens to be. If education is life, then the school must be life-giving; that is, it must make his body stronger, his mind more intelligent, and his spirit sweeter now, regardless of what he has learned or done. A teachers’ training class is maintained for mature students to become teachers, in which the most important work is the study of the development of the child, and what sort of an environment is necessary to secure a beautiful, unconscious, symmetrical development. “A sound, accomplished, beautiful body, a sympathetic, intelligent mind, a reverent spirit,” this is education. (pp. 602-603).

1911: Switch to Yearly Lecturing Tours

Gaston (2010) writes that in 1911, after Johnson “conducted a demonstration [summer] school at the University of Pennsylvania,” she set off to “engagements in New Jersey, New York, and the Midwest” (p. 61). I have been unable to find newspaper reports of lectures delivered by Johnson in New Jersey, or in New York City during the 1911 autumn. The October 11 and 13, 1911, *Washington Times* editions proclaim that she would speak on October 13 at a meeting of the Home and School Association of the Western High School. The *Bismarck Daily Tribune* (1911) reported the address and cited Johnson: “We make the school fit the needs of a child, not the child fit the needs of the school.” The newspaper noted that she gave a description of the school’s teachers’ training class. The *Washington Herald* (1911) quoted her at length:

When the school was opened four years ago...we had but six pupils, and when it opened last Monday for the year we had 100 pupils. The work that we have accomplished has proved that the system of compelling the child to meet the requirements of an iron-bound curriculum in school is wrong and that the purpose of the school should be to meet the needs of the child.

In November, the Boston *Christian Science Monitor* (1911) paid attention to Johnson’s school, “one of the most hopeful experimental schools of the country,” and stated that “the federation of women’s clubs” stood conspicuous “in the advancement of education in Alabama.” Proceedings of the 1911 Singletax Conference held in Chicago, November 24, 25 and 26, state that on November 25 a letter from Marietta Johnson was read stating that Mr. Fay Lewis from Illinois appealed for funds to help carry on Johnson’s school, that Joseph Fels in person seconded Lewis’ appeal, and that “\$182 was raised within a short time” (Singletax Conference, 1912, p. 24).

In December, famed journalist Edwin S. Potter (1911), who at the time resided in the single tax colony at Arden, Delaware reported in the *Syracuse Herald* that Marietta Johnson had conducted an extremely successful model class during the 1911 University of Pennsylvania Summer School. The students, that is, “a lot of backward and wayward misfits of the primary grades on whom the ordinary schools had failed utterly to make any satisfactory impression,” had the right to move about, talk while working, and gain a valuable learning experience in which the school did not repress their interests (see also Potter, 1912). Potter’s (1911) richly illustrated article reiterates many themes already discussed in Herring’s (1910) *Boston Daily Globe* piece on Johnson’s school. New was that Potter was the first to announce that Johnson was preparing to “establish a model school with normal training adjunct” in Arden in 1912. It seems that Johnson may have been planning to *first* spread her educational experiment among like-minded peers before branching out to other educators.

Finally in 1911, in December, *The Public* had “Organic Education” by Mariette [*sic*] L. Johnson (1911). She made an analogy between educating children and growing crops. The prudent “student of nature” (p. 1289) works in harmony with symptoms of health and disease of growing plants, analogous to

the work of doctors with patients. Johnson found schoolwork uneducational, since it did not “study the needs of the child as evidenced by the symptoms” (p. 1289). Hence children grow nervous, near-sighted, round-shouldered, and fail. Johnson asked rhetorical questions which she answered herself, and explicated her mission:

Why not act as reasonably in education as in other things? If the nature of the little child requires freedom, why not give freedom instead of requiring him to sit at stationary desks and be silent? If his nature requires out of doors, fresh air, why not give that? Can't he “learn” anything out of doors?...Why not sanely and bravely look the little child in the face, and throw away all the “traditions of the elders” and all of our unrighteous requirements, and simply and religiously meet *his* requirements? By the symptoms of his response or reaction. For the test of the environment is the reaction of the child. The test of a school is the condition of the child — bodily, mentally, spiritually. What does the body need? Fresh air in out-of-doors, play, freedom, no stationary desks, no enforced silence, but quiet — only when the occupation requires it; much choice in occupation, physical coordination through creative hand-work. What does the mind require? Time to observe, investigate, think and reason out a few things — often help and guidance from the teacher, but rarely ordered attention; experiences and activities in harmony with age and interests — that is, things of sense in the early years, books, experiences of others and abstractions in the later years. What is necessary for the spirit? Joy in work, a genuine desire to do it; work which enlists every part of the entire organism. In fact, all half-hearted work is insincere, and we often cultivate dishonesty in the child when we try to develop “will power” by arbitrary requirements...But can it be done? Why not? What is to prevent our taking the desks out of the room, allowing only twenty pupils to the teacher, and removing the “intellectual requirements” of the first grades in any city? Instead of desks, have tables at which the children may work. Instead of requirements in reading, writing, numbers, etc., let the children sing and play, make things of paper card board and textiles, taking care that the nervous system is not injured by too close work. Let them have gardens in which they may plant what they choose, and which they may care for in their own way with the sympathetic assistance of the teacher. Let them have stories of geography, history, and literature. Give them an opportunity to learn to speak some other modern language than their own. Let them have water colors and clay which they may freely use. Allow the teacher to take them out of doors at any hour she may wish, taking them to parks and museums for the pleasure and profit of going and seeing, rather than prepare them to “pass” any particular examination. Let them gain fundamental conceptions of numbers by the use of the rule, handling things, counting, estimating, weighing, measuring, etc. Let them hear beautiful poems recited by the teacher, and allow them to recite them also, but do not force the committing...Institutions to be educational must meet the demands of the individual, rather than make requirements which he must meet. An institution has no right to ask, “What do you know?” “What have you done?” “Where are your credentials?” But must ask, “What do you need?” “How may we serve you?” The “standards” of an institution are measured by its service, not by its requirements. Unless the individual emerges from the institution stronger of body, more intelligent of mind, sweeter and more helpful of spirit, the process has not been educational. (pp. 1289-1290).

1912: The First Acknowledgement on a National Scale

In the course of 1912, almost certainly due to decreasing school funds, a remarkable shift took place in Marietta Johnson's travel scheme. More and more often she would climb the pulpit, in a variety of cities, to inform her audience (who paid a fee of one dollar to listen to her expertise) about her school and its curriculum. Several journals devoted their columns to the ‘Fairhope Experiment’ (e.g., *American Educational Review*, *Current Literature*, *The Temple Artisan*), newspapers and magazines reported about Johnson's lectures (e.g., *Evening Star*, *New York Sun*, *Philadelphia Inquirer*, *Single Tax Review*, *Trenton Evening True American*, *Washington Herald*, *Washington Times*), the women's magazine *Pictorial Review* — nation-wide circulation of 700,000 copies — had a well-read multi-page illustrated article about the Fairhope School of Organic Education, Quaker magazine *Friends' Intelligencer* published a letter to the Editor about the school written by a distinguished journalist, and the West Coast newspaper *San Francisco Call* ran a richly illustrated article about Marietta Johnson's Summer School Camp in Arden, Delaware where she demonstrated her educational principles — an article that was reprinted by at least four influential

East Coast newspapers (*Boston Daily Globe*, *Brooklyn Daily Eagle*, *Buffalo Morning Express*, *Washington Herald*).

Before 1913, the Fairhope School of Organic Education, its educational principles and its curriculum were well known in many homes in the USA. Marietta Johnson had reached a firm reputation before the *New York Times* wrote about her and the school in March 1913.

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